

THE IMPACT OF APPLICATION OF WATER-SOLUBLE MINERAL FERTILIZERS ON BOLL WEIGHT OF COTTON UNDER FURROW AND DRIP IRRIGATION

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Abstract. *The paper presents data on the impact of application of conventional and water-soluble mineral fertilizers under furrow and drip irrigation on boll weight of upland cotton variety C-8286 in the condition of irrigated meadow-sierozem soils of Samarkand region.*

Keywords: *upland cotton variety C-8286, drip and furrow irrigation, boll weight of cotton plant.*

Introduction. The Ministry of Water Resources aims to expand the use of efficient irrigation technologies across 50% of Uzbekistan's irrigated agricultural land by 2030. As the adoption of drip irrigation technology rapidly increases, there is an urgent need to develop a new fertilization method for cotton that aligns with drip irrigation. Currently, the challenges include the inability to dissolve local phosphorus and potassium mineral fertilizers in water for use in drip irrigation, the high cost of fully water-soluble imported fertilizers, and the practice of applying 100% of the annual fertilizer rates before autumn plowing. This approach leads to cotton plants being unable to access the necessary phosphorus and potassium during their growing season, resulting in increased shedding of flowers and buds and ultimately causing reduced yields.

Drip irrigation focuses on delivering water directly to the plants rather than saturating the entire field. This method ensures that the soil layer surrounding the root zone receives adequate moisture and nutrients, which helps to minimize plant stress. As a result, plants can dedicate their energy primarily to growth and yield. In these optimal conditions, both the yield and fiber quality improve significantly.

M.Belousov and M.Jukova discovered that the potassium requirement of cotton rises during the fruiting stage. They found that applying potassium fertilizers during the squaring phase promotes healthy plant growth and development, minimizes the loss of fruit elements, and ultimately boosts yield [1].

D.Tungushova, B.Kamilov, and et al. observed that the growth and development of cotton under a drip irrigation system were enhanced, resulting in an increase of 3.0 bolls per plant compared to furrow irrigation, with each boll weighing 0.1 g higher. This method led to an additional cotton yield of 0.2-0.3 t ha⁻¹ on typical sierozem soils in the Tashkent region, and 0.6-0.7 t ha⁻¹ in the meadow-alluvial soils of the Republic of Karakalpakstan [4].

N.Ibragimov, B.Niyazaliev, and et al. determined that under typical sierozem soils, the application of granular fertilizers rich in calcium, calcium magnesium, and liquid nitrogen fertilizers containing copper, iron, and molybdenum at rates of P-140 and K-100 kg ha⁻¹ resulted in the highest cotton yields (ranging from 3.85 to 3.95 t ha⁻¹ and 3.79 to 3.90 t ha⁻¹). This approach created favorable conditions for providing cotton with essential nutrients such as nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, and microelements including copper, iron, molybdenum, calcium, and magnesium, thereby increasing overall seed cotton yield [3].

Materials and methods. The field experiments were conducted from 2021 to 2023 in the Ishtikhan district of the Samarkand region, in meadow-sierozem soils with a groundwater depth of 2.0 meters. Upland cotton variety C-8286 was studied, exploring two rates and timings of mineral fertilizers, along with furrow and drip irrigation methods. The field experiment was a split-split plot arrangement with irrigation methods on main plots, fertilizer application methods on sub-main plots and fertilizer rates randomized within submain plots. Each plot consisted of 8 rows, row spacing of 60 cm, and the experiment was replicated three times.

Results and discussions. The high yield of cotton varieties is directly associated with the boll weight of cotton, which in turn is influenced by irrigation technologies and the application rates of mineral fertilizers.

In the 2021 field experiment, the C-8286 cotton variety was cultivated using drip irrigation technology. When conventional mineral fertilizers were applied at rates of N-150, P-105, and K-75 kg ha⁻¹, the average boll weight for the first and second harvests was 5.4 g, with weights of 5.7 g and 4.2 g, respectively. In contrast, when mineral fertilizers were applied using the conventional method at rates of N-200, P-140, and K-100 kg ha⁻¹, the average boll weight increased to 5.4 g, with weights of 6.2 g and 4.6 g, reflecting a 0.5 g increase due to the additional 50 kg of nitrogen, 35 kg of phosphorus, and 25 kg of potassium per hectare. In treatments 3 and 4, where mineral fertilizers were fertigated during irrigation, the boll weights were 0.3 g and 0.2 g higher, respectively, compared to treatments 1 and 2 with conventional fertilizer applications. In treatments 5 and 6, where phosphorus and potassium fertilizers were applied before autumn plowing and nitrogen fertilizers at a rate of N-150 kg ha⁻¹ were used during the cotton growing period, the average boll weight was 5.5 g, with weights of 6.3 g and 4.7 g in the first and second harvests, respectively. Increasing the mineral fertilizer rates to N-200, P-140, and K-100 kg ha⁻¹ resulted in a further 0.3 g increase in boll weight compared to the treatment with N-150, P-105, and K-75 kg ha⁻¹.

In the 7th and 8th treatments of the drip irrigation experiment, water-soluble mineral fertilizers were applied in a form readily absorbed by the plants during each irrigation. This led to an increase in the boll weight of cotton. Application of N-150, P-105, K-75 kg ha⁻¹ enabled achieving the average boll weight of 5.9 g. When the mineral fertilizer rates were raised to N-200, P-140, K-100 kg ha⁻¹, the boll weight increased by an additional 0.2 g. Notably, applying mineral fertilizers directly to the root zone during each irrigation resulted in a 0.7 g increase in boll weight with N-150, P-105, K-75 kg ha⁻¹ compared to irrigations 3 and 4, while a 0.5 g increase was observed with the higher rates of N-200, P-140, K-100 kg ha⁻¹ (Figure 1).

In 2022, favorable weather conditions during the planting season led to early growth and a successful cotton yield. While the number of bolls increased compared to the previous year, the weight of cotton per boll was slightly lower due to nutrient distribution among the yield components. However, the overall cotton yield was higher due to the increased number of bolls.

The highest boll weight was observed in treatment 8, which utilized drip irrigation and received water-soluble mineral fertilizers at rates of N-200, P-140, and K-100 kg ha⁻¹. In the first harvest, the boll weight was recorded at 6.1 g, with an average of 5.3 g across all harvests. Notably, this was 1.1-1.2 g higher than the control treatment 2 (Figure 1).

Figure-1. Effect of application of water-soluble fertilizers under different irrigation technologies on boll weight of cotton, g

In 2023, the highest boll weight of cotton was recorded in treatment 8, where drip irrigation and water-soluble mineral fertilizers were applied at rates of N-200, P-140, and K-100 kg ha⁻¹. The boll weight was 6.4 g and 5.2 g for the first and second harvests, respectively, resulting in an average weight of 5.8 g across the harvests.

Conclusion. In the treatments where water-soluble fertilizers were applied through drip irrigation, a notable increase in boll weight of cotton was recorded, resulting in higher yields. This is attributed to the application of water-soluble fertilizers directly to the root zone, allowing for easy uptake by the plants. Consequently, the cotton plants were able to accumulate more fruit elements, leading to an increase in seed cotton yield.

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